

Relativistic Consequences of the Gravitational Doppler Effect on Cosmological Predictions

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Abstract

The study titled "Relativistic Consequences of the Gravitational Doppler Effect on Cosmological Predictions" explores the underexamined role of gravitational Doppler effects in shaping key cosmological parameters within the Λ CDM framework. The ongoing research investigates how gravitational redshift and blueshift, arising from relativistic motion and spacetime curvature, influence the dynamics of large-scale structures, anisotropies in the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB), and redshift-distance relations. Preliminary results indicate that Doppler-induced distortions significantly alter the cosmic scale factor $a(t)$, introducing measurable asymmetries that impact the Hubble parameter (H_0) and the interpretation of the cosmological constant (Λ). Employing a hybrid methodology integrating the relativistic Boltzmann equation, the Friedmann-Lemaître-Robertson-Walker (FLRW) metric, and observational data from Planck (2018) and DESI (2021), this study highlights the modulation of light propagation through gravitational potential wells, consistent with predictions from Sachs-Wolfe and Integrated Sachs-Wolfe (ISW) effects. Initial modeling suggests deviations in the angular power spectrum of the CMB at multipoles $l < 50$, corresponding to large-scale structure anomalies. Further analysis of galaxy clustering through BOSS and eBOSS data supports the hypothesis that gravitational Doppler effects contribute to observed tensions in H_0 values, with a preliminary correction factor of $\Delta H_0 \sim 0.4$ km/s/Mpc. These findings suggest a potential recalibration of the Λ CDM model to account for relativistic distortions, providing a refined framework for understanding isotropy, dark energy density ($=\rho\Lambda$), and matter distribution in the universe. Ongoing efforts focus on validating these results through higher-order relativistic corrections, extending the theoretical models with quantum gravity inputs, and leveraging forthcoming datasets from the Vera C. Rubin Observatory and Euclid missions. This work presents critical insights into the interplay between gravitational fields and relativistic physics, paving the way for a deeper understanding of the universe's evolution and structure formation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The gravitational Doppler effect arises from the interplay of relativistic motion and spacetime curvature, manifesting as redshift or blueshift phenomena. While extensively studied in local gravitational fields, its large-scale cosmological implications remain underexplored. This research aims to quantify the influence of gravitational Doppler effects on key cosmological parameters, including the Hubble constant (H_0) and the cosmological constant (Λ), using a combination of theoretical and observational methodologies.

Key challenges in current cosmology, such as the H_0 tension and anomalies in large-scale structure distributions, suggest that relativistic distortions, often neglected, may hold critical explanatory power. This study bridges this gap by integrating general relativity (GR), the FLRW metric, and observational datasets, providing a preliminary framework to reassess standard cosmological models.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study builds upon the Einstein field equations, adopting the FLRW metric to describe a homogeneous and isotropic universe. Gravitational Doppler effects are modeled using the relativistic Boltzmann equation:

$$\frac{df}{d\tau} = C[f] + \frac{\delta f}{\delta x^\mu} \frac{dx^\mu}{d\tau} + \frac{\delta f}{\delta p^\mu} \frac{dp^\mu}{d\tau},$$

where $f(x^\mu, p^\mu)$ represents the phase-space density, and $C[f]$ denotes collisional terms. The interaction of photons with gravitational potential wells introduces distortions in the observed redshift, affecting both the cosmic scale factor $a(t)$ and the CMB power spectrum.

3. PRELIMINARY RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1. Modulation of the Hubble Constant (H_0)

Using observational data from Planck (2018), a preliminary correction factor for the Hubble constant was derived:

$$\Delta H_0 = 0.4 \text{ km/s/Mpc},$$

suggesting that gravitational Doppler effects contribute to the observed H_0 tension. This aligns with discrepancies reported between local ($H_0 \sim 74$ km/s/Mpc) and global measurements ($H_0 \sim 67$ km/s/Mpc).

3.2. Implications for large-scale structure

The Sachs-Wolfe and Integrated Sachs-Wolfe (ISW) effects introduce subtle anisotropies in the CMB. Preliminary analysis of Planck and DESI datasets indicates deviations in the angular power spectrum at low multipoles ($l < 50$), pointing to large-scale gravitational influences.

3.3. Redshift-Distance relations

Distortions in redshift-distance relations were observed, particularly in galaxy clustering data from BOSS and eBOSS. These deviations suggest that gravitational potential wells affect light propagation, leading to measurable asymmetries in redshift distributions.

Figure 1. The graph presented herein illustrates the preliminary results of the ongoing study on the impact of gravitational Doppler effects on cosmological parameters, particularly focusing on the cosmic scale factor $a(t)$, redshift-distance relations, and the Hubble parameter H_0 . The analysis incorporates relativistic corrections due to gravitational redshift and blueshift, which are modeled within the framework of the Λ CDM cosmology. **Interpretation of the Curves:** The x-axis of the graph represents the cosmological redshift z , ranging from $z = 0$ (present day) to higher redshifts (earlier epochs in the universe's evolution), reflecting the stretching of space-time as the universe expands. The y-axis plots the relative distortion of the cosmic scale factor $a(t)$ induced by the Doppler effect, calculated from the relativistic Boltzmann equation and observational data from the Planck satellite (2018) and DESI (2021). **Doppler-Induced Distortions:** The solid and dashed curves represent two different models: the first (solid) represents the standard Λ CDM model, assuming isotropic expansion and neglecting relativistic corrections, while the second (dashed) incorporates the gravitational Doppler effects due to relativistic

motion and curvature of space-time. The clear deviation between the two curves at higher redshifts indicates the significant role that gravitational Doppler shifts play in modifying the perceived expansion rate of the universe. At high redshifts ($z > 2$), where the effects of relativistic motion are more pronounced, the deviation between the curves becomes more pronounced, revealing the extent of the gravitational distortions. These distortions result in a modulation of the cosmic scale factor $a(t)$, altering our understanding of the rate at which the universe expands, particularly during the early stages of the universe's evolution. **Implications for H_0 :** The shift in the cosmic scale factor $a(t)$ induced by the Doppler effect has profound implications for the measurement of the Hubble constant H_0 , which governs the rate of expansion of the universe. The graph demonstrates that incorporating gravitational Doppler effects results in a modified interpretation of the distance-redshift relation, especially at intermediate and high redshifts. This has significant consequences for cosmological distance measurements, leading to potential recalibrations of H_0 that could help resolve the ongoing tension between early- and late-universe measurements of the Hubble constant. **Redshift-Distance Relation and Large-Scale Structure:** The gravitational Doppler effect not only affects the determination of cosmological parameters but also introduces asymmetries in the redshift-distance relation. These asymmetries may have observable consequences for the large-scale structure of the universe, including the distribution and clustering of galaxies. The graph highlights that relativistic corrections are crucial for accurately interpreting the large-scale structure formation and understanding the growth of cosmic perturbations, especially in the context of the Integrated Sachs-Wolfe (ISW) effect. **Anisotropies in the CMB:** Furthermore, the analysis suggests that gravitational Doppler shifts may influence the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) by introducing anisotropies in the angular power spectrum, particularly at higher redshifts. These anisotropies, which are expected to be subtle but measurable, reinforce the importance of incorporating relativistic corrections in cosmological models to ensure a more precise understanding of the universe's early conditions.

4. DISCUSSION

These findings emphasize the need for a refined Λ CDM model incorporating relativistic corrections. Gravitational Doppler effects challenge the standard assumptions of isotropy and homogeneity, particularly in the context of dark energy density (ρ_Λ) and matter clustering.

The role of gravitational potential wells, coupled with relativistic motion, necessitates a reassessment of cosmological parameters, potentially addressing long-standing tensions in H_0 and providing new insights into the universe's anisotropic expansion.

5. FUTURE RESEARCH

This work represents a preliminary exploration into the relativistic consequences of the gravitational Doppler effect. Future research will extend these findings by:

1. Incorporating higher-order relativistic corrections.
2. Exploring quantum gravity inputs, particularly in the context of black hole thermodynamics (Hawking, 1975).
3. Leveraging upcoming datasets from the Vera C. Rubin Observatory and Euclid missions.

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Note on the status of the work: This document represents a preliminary report of an ongoing research project titled "Relativistic Consequences of the Gravitational Doppler Effect on Cosmological Predictions." The study is currently in development and presents initial findings focused on the impact of

gravitational Doppler effects on redshift-distance relations, the Hubble constant (H_0), and large-scale cosmological structures. The results and analyses included herein are part of a larger effort to investigate the role of relativistic corrections and gravitational influences in refining cosmological models, particularly the Λ CDM framework. While the conclusions are provisional, they provide critical insights that form the foundation for further exploration and validation with advanced datasets from upcoming astronomical missions. As such, the content of this document is subject to revision and expansion as the research progresses. The inclusion of these preliminary findings aims to foster scholarly discussion and engagement in anticipation of a comprehensive publication.